

AMOC Restoration through Spatially Targeted Geoengineering Technologies

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Abstract

The Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) is at risk of significant weakening or collapse due to freshwater input from Greenland ice sheet melt and Arctic sea-ice loss. Stable surface freshwater lenses formed in this process suppress deep convection in the Labrador and Irminger Seas. Unlike existing geoengineering proposals that require enormous costs or intervene in global atmospheric processes, this work presents a spatially targeted, locally applied, and relatively low-cost alternative : deliberate modification of the freshwater export regime from Greenland fjords to promote vertical mixing rather than surface stratification. By deploying floating curtains in the mouths of selected fjords (partially blocking the upper 50 m while allowing turbulent exchange at depth), seasonal pulsed surface runoff can be transformed into a quasi-continuous, vertically mixed outflow.

The denser (more saline) outflow during ebb tide generates density anomalies that initiate mesoscale anticyclonic vortices through baroclinic instability, leading to local surface salinization, Ekman convergence, thinning of the freshwater cap, and preconditioning for renewed deep winter convection in the Labrador Sea.

The proposed mechanism harnesses the potential energy of freshwater runoff and tidal energy to drive saltwater upwelling in mixed plumes, thereby destabilizing stratification. If validated through pilot experiments, such local interventions could contribute to stabilizing deep convection and supporting AMOC recovery.

Keywords: AMOC collapse, Greenland ice sheet, freshwater runoff, fjord curtain, thermohaline circulation, geoengineering, proglacial lake drainage, sea level rise

1. Introduction

In October 2024, 44 leading climatologists addressed the governments of northern countries (Open Letter by Climate Scientists, 2024). The letter indicated that the risk of the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) stopping is underestimated and could have catastrophic consequences, with severe global impacts. Currently, these countries see the collapse of the AMOC as an existential challenge at the national level (CNN, 2025), and scientists estimate the probability of its stopping, given rising emissions, at 70% (Drijfhout et al., 2025).

Research highlights the effect of freshwater from the Greenland ice sheet in suppressing thermohaline convection in the Irminger and Labrador Seas (Boers, 2021; Ditlevsen and Ditlevsen, 2023). According to Shepherd et al. (2020) and Otosaka et al. (2023), more than 50% of the ice sheet's mass loss comes from surface runoff caused by direct melting. Besides blocking the AMOC, Greenland's ongoing glacier melting also contributes to rising global sea levels (Shepherd et al., 2020). This further increases storm damage along the US coast, driven by sea level rise from reduced Gulf Stream outflow, thermal expansion, and storm surges (Volkov et al., 2023; AOML, 2023).

A possible model for changes in the Greenland ice sheet concentrates on the island's southwestern coast. Here, glaciers have retreated inland (Meire et al., 2023; Williams et al., 2024), and calving along with subglacial runoff occur on the surface and within fjord depths (Straneo and Cenedese, 2015). The nearby Labrador Sea is covered by a stable layer of freshened water (Chen et al., 2024). It is evident that this water, which impedes circulation, escapes into the ocean through the fjords. Notably, surface runoff poses a significant threat (Yang et al., 2016): icebergs melt gradually, releasing water at various depths (Moon et al., 2018; Davison et al., 2020), and the runoff forms

large, stable lenses that are only weakly prone to mixing. This process occurs seasonally, in late summer and autumn, just before the winter overturning (van Westen and Baatsen, 2025).

The climate impact of AMOC shutdown (van Westen and Baatsen, 2025), along with the threat of sea level rise (Nicholls et al., 2024), affects the wealthiest and most industrialised countries. It's not just about Europe: if the AMOC were to stop, India could lose up to 70% of its rainfall (Germanwatch, 2024). These effects are so significant that, in addition to global efforts to reduce carbon dioxide emissions, geoengineering projects have been proposed. These include underwater curtains (Wolovick and Moore, 2018), glacier coverings (Field et al., 2018), and dams (Siegert et al., 2024).

Such projects are currently under debate due to their scale and cost. Additionally, many scientists oppose interference in climate processes, emphasising the risks (Li et al., 2023). These concerns are seen as the main obstacle, as blocking the flow of freshwater from Greenland could impede the restoration of the AMOC/Gulf Stream.

The main issue with Greenland's freshwater runoff isn't its total volume but rather how it is delivered to the ocean: currently, this runoff mostly takes the form of seasonal, surface-trapped lenses that consistently inhibit vertical mixing and deep convection. In this discussion, we explore the possibility of a purposeful change in the regime of freshwater export from fjords — from pulsed and superficial to quasi-stationary and vertically mixed — and discuss the potential oceanographic consequences of such a shift. We intentionally avoid providing numerical estimates of the salinity or density of the resulting water, as these parameters are emergent properties of the system and cannot be reliably measured without field experiments.

2. Concept

The proposed intervention does not involve altering climatic or atmospheric processes in their usual sense. Instead, it focuses on the local management of the boundary condition at the interface between the fjord and the shelf — the area where glacial freshwater runoff is converted into an oceanic signal. We do not plan to intervene in open ocean circulation, radiation balance, or atmospheric dynamics; our focus is solely on changes to the geometry, depth, and regime of freshwater export from the fjords. We argue that implementing a solution to reduce the negative impacts of freshwater runoff is practical, technically feasible, and financially achievable.

The purpose of this document is to promote a broad discussion. To address runoff and surface lens formation, we propose a comprehensive approach involving two methods.

2.1. Fjord Curtain System

The first method involves blocking one of the fjords at its exit to the ocean, in an area protected from storms. A floating curtain is used from shore to shore, from the surface down to a depth of 50 metres, and is securely anchored to shoreline supports. The upper edge, from 2 metres below the surface to 1 metre above the water, is rigid, capable of holding back freshened water but designed to capsize under heavy loads, allowing ice and debris to pass.

From 2 to 40 metres deep, it is a polyethylene-reinforced curtain; from 40 to 50 metres, it features numerous vertical openings. This design maximizes turbulence in both incoming and outgoing water and promotes mixing. Below 50 metres, the curtain is absent, allowing free flow and the release of hydraulic pressure, deep-water exchange, and the passage of marine organisms.

The freshened water mass collecting in the fjord flows through the slots at the bottom of the curtain. This process is driven by two energy sources: the potential energy of the freshened water and the mechanical energy of tidal exchange. Exiting into the ocean side of fjord at a depth of 50 metres, this

mixture rises to the surface due to its lower density compared to the surrounding seawater. We expect the surface mixture to have a salinity close to that of the layer at 50 metres depth. Salinity regulation can be achieved by adjusting the curtain's depth and using multiple curtains in sequence. Accurate data can only be obtained through in-situ experiments.

The rising mixture faces constant pressure from beneath and must flow sideways. Since the curtain and shores enclose it on three sides, it eventually flows into the ocean. This creates a continuous, unidirectional current moving toward the sea, with maximum power occurring during the ebb tide.

The goal of this document is not to develop a detailed model but to establish a principle: the freshwater entering the fjords from the ice sheet possesses potential energy in a physical sense. By harnessing this energy, we can lift saltwater from depth in a mixture, thereby increasing the salinity of the surface layer. Additionally, this water will ascend not only to the point of neutral buoyancy but also higher, due to the hydraulic head created by the formation of mixed water at the lower boundary of the curtain; it will erode and carry away the surface layer, which cannot be replenished from the fjord side. Critically, the curtain acts as a temporal buffer: rather than releasing freshwater as a single summer surface pulse, it stores the meltwater and releases it as a quasi-continuous, vertically mixed outflow through autumn and winter. This shifts vortex formation toward the pre-convective and convective seasons, extending the window of active preconditioning to coincide with the onset of deep winter convection in the Labrador Sea.

It is believed that removing the desalinated layer of water from the sea surface is necessary, but what if it is enough to "seed salt grains" above the stream of warm Atlantic water to restart the process?

The key engineering challenge is ensuring the strength of the curtain under significant hydrostatic pressure from the fjord side. The curtain is positioned deep within the fjord (about 10 km from the open ocean), in an area protected from storms and ocean swells, where wave action is minimal. To reduce risks from icebergs and pack ice, it is proposed to start pilot experiments in fjords with land-terminating glaciers, where significant calving is absent and freshwater runoff is mainly due to surface and river melting. In such fjords, the threat of impact from large ice floes is virtually eliminated.

To minimize iceberg calving, a second method may be applied.

2.2 Dynamics of oceanic processes

Due to the upwelling of more saline water, estuarine circulation, and tidal exchange, a density anomaly forms in the fjord—a non-stratified layer of water from the surface down to 50 metres, with salinity and temperature similar to those of ocean water at the lower edge of the curtain. During ebb tides, water from the fjord, including that accumulated through the rise of mixed water, exits into the ocean.

Typically, fjords supply highly freshened water that spreads across the surface, a phenomenon well documented in scientific literature and modeling. In this case, the water exiting the fjord is denser than the surface layer of the ocean. This flow creates a density front (Flynn & Linden, 2006). In contact zones with the surrounding fresher water, turbulence and Kelvin-Helmholtz instabilities develop, and filament detachment occurs (Smyth & Moum, 2012).

Since the surrounding freshened water is typically colder, these filaments, due to the mechanism of double diffusion, cool more quickly than they lose their salinity and sink into the saline layer even to a greater depth (Schmitt, 1994). This results in a local thickening of the saline water layer, the extent of which depends on the volume of a single water discharge from the fjord during ebb tide. For fjords with an area of 100–200 sq km, the volume of the tidal prism is 0.2–0.4 cubic km. If this water is

spread over the surface of the stratified layer in the ocean at a depth of 50–70 metres as a lens 10 metres thick, it forms a spot 5–7 kilometres in diameter, even without considering the entrainment of less saline surface water.

This size corresponds to the Rossby radius in the Labrador Sea (Rieck et al., 2019), which facilitates the formation of an anticyclonic vortex through baroclinic instability (Feng et al., 2021). Importantly, the saline lens does not rotate in isolation within its 10-metre thickness but interacts hydraulically with the underlying homogeneous saline layer of the ocean. The surface disturbance generates a horizontal pressure gradient that extends downward through the entire homogeneous layer (Yankovsky et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2024). During barotropization, baroclinic energy converts into barotropic energy, allowing the vortex to develop a vertically coherent structure (Meunier et al., 2023). The upper boundary of the saline layer is likely situated beneath the fresh layer, at approximately 50 metres depth. The lower boundary is defined by the depth of the involved column of homogeneous water. Rotation elevates the centre of the 5–7 kilometre diameter lens, reducing its separation from the surface to about 20–30 metres, which facilitates wave mixing.

The subsurface anticyclonic vortex also generates Ekman convergence in the overlying freshwater layer through viscous coupling at the interface (McGillicuddy, 2016). Fresh water is drawn horizontally toward the vortex center and undergoes downwelling, where it mixes with the saline water of the vortex core. This process gradually thins and destabilizes the surface freshwater cap, creating conditions favorable for deep winter convection and breakthrough of the convective vortex to the surface, where its cooling rate and internal convection become maximal.

Furthermore, the repeated discharge of saline water from the fjord may cause the formation of closely spaced vortices with similar density and size. At a certain distance between vortex centers, a vortex merger occurs — a process in which two co-rotating vortices combine into a larger, more stable vortex (Griffiths & Hopfinger, 2018; Le Vu et al., 2018).

Of course, not every ebb tide will lead to the formation of a new vortex, and this process itself requires multiple validations both through models and in field conditions. However, the aim of this manuscript is to specifically outline the sequence of scientifically supported effects that require thorough verification.

In effect, the introduction of saline water in the manner described promotes the formation of a mesoscale vortex, salinization of the surface layer, a drop in temperature at the vortex core, upwelling of saline waters, and bending of isopycnals. It can also be suggested that there is a weakening of vertical stratification and a reduction in the influence of freshwater runoff. All these factors align with the well-known phenomenon of preconditioning in the Labrador Sea, which is a crucial factor for initiating deep convection.

The mixing of fresh water and the reduction of its fraction is not the primary goal of this project. Its effectiveness is assessed by the number of anticyclonic vortices created, which, according to observations, are capable of drifting significant distances (Bosse et al., 2016), persisting for months to years (Gula et al., 2019), and, most importantly, "Submesoscale processes modulate this transport and in turn the stratification of the Labrador Sea interior, by controlling the characteristics of the coherent vortices formed along West Greenland" (Tagklis et al., 2020). The relevant metric here is not the volume of water exchanged but the area of ocean preconditioned for convection. Each vortex acts as a sustained mixer over tens of square kilometers, gradually eroding the surface freshwater cap and replacing it with saltier, warmer water from below — a process that continues for months after vortex formation. Since deep convection is a threshold phenomenon initiated in localized sites rather than requiring uniform surface transformation, even a modest number of such vortices may be sufficient to trigger and sustain it across the Labrador Sea interior.

The successful implementation of this project, which requires independent verification, could help restart deep convection in the Labrador Sea and contribute to stabilising and accelerating the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation. This research does not aim to provide a quantitative description or assess the project's readiness for the proposed approach. Its goal is to identify a physically grounded yet under-researched class of mechanisms related to controlling the regime of freshwater export from fjords and to promote discussion on their potential experimental validation. Given the possible consequences of AMOC degradation, even small-scale field experiments in individual fjords appear justified from both scientific and practical viewpoints.

The subsurface anticyclonic vortex in the Northern Hemisphere tends to move along isobaths and shift toward deeper waters. It is thought that this vortex, cooled from above while accessing warm water from below, exhibits a Carnot-like behaviour, which helps it grow and develop. Both of these ideas provide important support for the argument that the system encourages the start of deep convection. However, these theoretical notions still need to be tested in the field.

3. Discussion

The numerical modelling of the proposed mechanism presents a fundamental methodological challenge. A recent state-of-the-art simulation of AMOC tipping behaviour required 4,400 model years and six months of continuous computation on 1,024 processor cores of a national supercomputer (van Westen and Baatsen, 2025) — and this without accounting for the hypothetical processes and inevitable variability described in the present work.

The proposed mechanism comprises several sequential levels. The first involves the formation of filaments at the curtain outlet, with critically varying salinity for each fjord and each day of the year. The second is the upwelling of water in the outer part of the fjord and the accumulation of a salinized layer. The third is the release of this layer into the open ocean through ebb-tide flow, the formation of a density anomaly patch, its subsequent sinking and lateral spreading. The fourth is the formation of anticyclonic vortices in the Labrador Sea, their migration, and their influence on the preconditioning of deep convection. Only then does the effect propagate to global thermohaline circulation.

Parameterising each of these levels and transferring them into coupled climate models is an extremely complex undertaking, as nonlinear feedbacks operate at each level, continuously modifying the properties of the flows — most critically, salinity. Under these conditions, any attempt to provide an approximate numerical estimate of the effect without prior theoretical development would be methodologically unsound. Formulating a well-posed modelling problem requires first developing and validating the hypothesis at the theoretical level — which is the purpose of the present work.

Restoring AMOC might boost Greenland snowfall; thicker snow cover can conceal dark ice, decreasing albedo feedback and slowing melting, which could lead to more ice accumulation and a drop in sea levels. Increased evaporation transfers heat to upper atmospheric layers, where it radiates into space, cooling the surface. The main aim is to stabilise deep convection and AMOC circulation; however, feasibility and the necessary scale are still open questions requiring experimentation, monitoring, and multidisciplinary cooperation.

3.1. Methodological Rationale

In this work, quantitative estimates and numerical simulations of the processes are intentionally omitted. Current climate models require the parameterization of small-scale interactions that remain theoretically underdetermined under existing conditions. Any attempt to introduce numerical

estimates at this stage would inevitably lead to the artificial tuning of parameters to fit expected results, masking the lack of fundamental knowledge regarding the mechanics of the process.

We postulate that before proceeding to a computational description, it is necessary to verify the physical consistency of the proposed chain: "engineering solution — local hydrodynamic effect — global response." The proposed technology is aimed at forming measurable density anomalies by modifying the vertical profile of salinity and temperature. Numerical modeling is a secondary stage, which becomes meaningful only after verifying the theoretical sequence and obtaining empirical data on flow dynamics and mixing efficiency at the curtain interface through field experiments at the local scale—meters or tens of meters under real tidal conditions.

Conflict of Interest

The author declares that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

The author confirms being the sole contributor of this work and has approved it for publication.

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